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Production of large-size CCM plates

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ABSTRACT

Carbide-carbon materials (CCM) are a novel family of composites with high thermal conductivity and low density, of important interest for applications in high-energy particle physics (HEP) and in industrial applications that include, for example, thermal management systems, nuclear energy and aerospace. However, the high production costs are limiting, so far, their application for big series productions.

There are two ways, investigated within WP4, for an effective cost reduction: the first one is related to the increase of the material volume produced in each machine cycle. The second way involves a decrease of the production temperature, thus reducing the energy consumed during the cycle, as well as decreasing the consumption of elements such as moulds and electrodes.

This deliverable addresses the first way of cost reduction, targeting the increase of the volume of sintered material in a single machine cycle, to be achieved by doubling the sintered disk cross-section area (up to $\sim 400 \text{ cm}^2$). However, in the first 24 months of the project, as documented in the internal I.FAST milestone MS14, the team also worked, in parallel, on the second aspect of cost reduction, lowering the sintering temperature. The composites sintered in big dimensions in

the scope of D4.4 thus combine both aspects: they are increased in size, and produced at a lowered temperature.

I.FAST Consortium, 2023

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

This document summarizes the work done in the first two years within I.FAST WP4.4 to achieve the project deliverable D4.4 “Production of large-size (Carbide-Carbon Materials) CCM plates: Produce two large CCM plates (cross section >400 cm²) in a single sintering cycle”.

Chapter 1 gives a context to the research work, and summarizes the objective of the project, and of the specific deliverable.

Chapter 2 presents the state of the art on CCM prior to I.FAST, and reports the main limitations, in terms of production times and costs, of the Molybdenum-Graphite (MoGr) CCM.

Chapter 3 focuses on the development of Chromium-Graphite (CrGr), a cheaper alternative to MoGr. It reports the initial sintering trials and the material characterization, for a configuration involving the production Ø170 mm plates.

Chapter 4 is dedicated to the description of the actions put in place to reach the deliverable D4.4, and to the successful sintering of two Ø230 mm CrGr plates in a single machine cycle. Results in terms of employed power and energy, savings of mould elements, and density / electrical conductivity properties, are presented.

Chapter 5 summarizes the main conclusions and presents the plans for future activities in the scope of WP4.4.

1 Introduction

The objective of WP4.4 is to develop and industrialize materials with low density and high thermal, mechanical and electrical properties. In recent years, at CERN, novel Carbide-Carbon Materials (CCM) have been developed, to combine the electrical conductivity and ductility of metals and some carbides, with the low density and good thermal conductivity of graphite [1]. Such combination of properties is very interesting for applications in High-Energy Physics (HEP), for example in the case of beam-intercepting devices (BID). As proved also by past contacts with external companies and institutes and the CERN Knowledge Transfer (KT) [2], this combination of properties is also very desirable for industrial and societal applications such as thermal management applications, aerospace, nuclear energy production. Main properties and material parameters have been collected at the beginning of the I.FAST project, within WP4.4, and put together into a technical specification, which defines the target requirements for the CCM to be produced. The technical specification is reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Target thermophysical properties for the CCM developed in the scope of WP4.4.

Property	ρ^*	ρ	Unit
Density at 20°C	2.40 – 2.60		[g/cm ³]
Specific heat at 20°C	> 0.6		[J/(g·K)]

Electrical conductivity at 20°C	> 0.75		[MS/m]
Thermal Diffusivity 20°C / 300°C	> 350/100	> 20/6	[mm ² /s]
Thermal conductivity at 20°C / 300°C	> 500/280	> 35/20	[W/(m·K)]
Volumetric CTE 20-1000°C	< 7		[10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹]
Coefficient of thermal expansion 20-1000°C	< 2.9	< 15	[10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹]
Young's Modulus at 20°C	35 < E < 75	5 < E < 8	[GPa]
Flexural strength at 20°C	> 60	> 10	[MPa]
Flexural strain to rupture at 20°C	> 2500	> 4000	[µm/m]
Dimensional stability*	< 0.05	< 0.25	%

**The dimensional stability shall be ensured after the following thermal cycle: heating of the specimen up to 1950°C with a ramp of 5°C/min. Cooling of the specimen down to room temperature with the same ramp.*

A material that would fit with such properties is Molybdenum-Graphite (MoGr) [3], a CCM already successfully developed within previous European projects such as ARIES (WP14 & WP17) [4], and industrially produced and installed in LHC secondary collimators in 2018/20 [5], in the framework of the HL-LHC project [6]. However, the use of MoGr in big series, for example for industrial applications, is hindered by its production cost. In 2020, the cost estimation for MoGr was in the order of 16÷20 €/cm³ for a precisely-finished component, one order of magnitude higher than in the case of copper. Isostatic graphite, another low-density material with good thermal transport properties, is more expensive than copper, but still a factor 4-5 cheaper than MoGr. To understand the reasons of the high price of CCM materials, it is useful to refer to the full production cycle, from the base constituents to the finished product, reported in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – CCM production cycle.

As can be seen, the process is laborious, involving many production steps. The most expensive step is the Spark Plasma Sintering cycle (SPS). The main parameters impacting on the cost of an SPS cycle are:

- **Power/energy consumption of the cycle**, related to the high sintering temperature (>2600°C) and dwell time (~7h before start of the cool-down).
- **Consumable mould**, made of expensive graphite. In fact, at such high temperatures, and also due to the higher coefficient of thermal expansion of the mould with respect to MoGr, the mould contracts too much during cooldown and traps the sintered MoGr plate, and needs to be destroyed to extract the plate at the end of the process.

The proposed strategy for a more efficient, sustainable and cheap production process is:

- **Increase the volume of the CCM sintered per cycle.** The power consumption is weakly dependent on the amount of sintered material, because the sintered volume represents less than 10% of the total heated volume that is heated up and dissipates energy. This means that, increasing the sintered volume by expanding the sintered cross-section, height and number of plates translates into a power consumption scaling down almost linearly. As a positive side effect, bigger plates also mean upscaling the size of the final component, for those applications which require components of large size.
- **Decrease the CCM sintering temperature.** A decrease of the sintering temperature directly translates to a decrease in the power consumption, since power and temperature are proportional. Additionally, for the same heat-up ramp, the cycle time is also lower, as the required sintering temperature is reached earlier. Since the energy is the product of power and time, a decrease in the sintering temperature translates into an energy consumption scaling down quadratically. Moreover, reducing the sintering temperature down to 2000°C

or less also permits to save the mould elements which would be consumable at each cycle with a standard process, with an additional significant cost reduction per cycle.

As a side note, the authors also want to stress that efficient production processes shall become more and more the target of research institutes and industry, the economic reason being only one of the many motivations (moral, ethical and political).

Whereas the increase of sintered volume of CCM per cycle can be done by acting on the configuration of the SPS machine and mould, decreasing the CCM sintering temperature is more complex. In fact, the sintering temperature is related to the melting of the metal carbide phase, which in the case of MoGr is indeed above 2600°C. This means that, to achieve similar properties at lower temperature, an alternative precursor to molybdenum must be found: such precursor should combine with the carbon of graphite into carbide with a lower melting temperature than the molybdenum carbide, still acting as catalysers of the final composite graphitization. In the first year of the project, WP4.4 thus focused on chromium as an alternative to molybdenum, with the goal of replacing MoGr with Chromium-Graphite (CrGr) [7]. Chromium carbide possesses a lower melting temperature with respect to molybdenum carbide, allowing a liquid-phase sintering at temperatures equal or lower than 2000 °C. First essays with the sintering of CrGr were done at Brevetti Bizz during ARIES, WP14 and WP17 [8]; the material was promising on the thermal point of view, but extremely low in mechanical strength, presenting a maximum bending strength in the order of 10 MPa in the base plane directions. Such a low mechanical strength, on top of restricting the possible use of the material to applications with little to no applied mechanical stress, also prevents an effective machining of the material, as it easily breaks during this operation. Scope of the work during the first year of IFAST WP4.4 was to improve the mechanical properties of the material by at least a factor of 5, to prove its possible use as a valid, cheaper alternative to MoGr.

Table 2 gives a qualitative estimation on the possible total cost reduction for different options of produced volume and material type. In any case, Producing two plates with Ø230 mm fulfils the requirements of deliverable D4.4 (~400 cm² of cross section).

Table 2. Qualitative estimation of cost reduction for different options of produced materials and sizes.

Option identifier	Material	Plate size	N. plates produced in the same cycle	Normalized Price*
#1	MoGr	Ø170 mm	2	100%
#2	MoGr	Ø230 mm	2	~90 %
#3	CrGr	Ø170 mm	2	~80 %

#4	CrGr	Ø230 mm	2	~70 %
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* Estimation for an industrial production of at least 50 plates, including fine machining. To be confirmed after testing.

2 Our starting point: Molybdenum-Graphite

The state of the art prior to the beginning of I.FAST for CCM was MoGr. This material was produced in series by Nanoker, for use in CERN primary and secondary collimators, in the period 2018/20. The initial configuration, at the beginning of the series production period, allowed sintering a single Ø170 mm plate per machine cycle. In parallel with the production of the first tens of blocks, CERN and Nanoker worked together at an upscale at the production capacity, with the goal of doubling the number of Ø170 mm plates produced per cycle [10]. This attempt was successful; thermophysical tests performed on the material produced with the Ø170 mm – double plate cycle, proved that the MoGr properties of the upscaled configuration were comparable to the single-plate cycle results.

At the beginning of I.FAST, the achievable CCM sintering capacity was thus two plates Ø170 mm, thickness 25 mm, in a single sintering cycle (Option #1 of Table 2). The sintering configuration is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 2 – Schematic configuration of the double Ø170 mm plate sintering of CCM. Note that the sintering starts from two MoGr green bodies, pre-compacted at room temperature, with thickness of 48 mm that, after sintering is compacted down to ~25 mm. Each green body is hosted in a graphite mould, which must be replaced after each cycle.

Figure 3 – Left: view of the two graphite moulds prior to insertion in the machine. Middle: the two graphite moulds are wrapped with insulating internal soft carbon felt. Right: the structure is then further wrapped with an insulating external soft carbon felt.

This method of production gives very good thermophysical result on the MoGr CCM; for this reason, the material, on top of being adopted for HL-LHC primary and secondary collimators, is also being studied in other research institutes. For example, KEK is testing MoGr samples for potential use in the SuperKEKb collimation system. Additionally, contacts with external companies for industrial applications are being coordinated by the CERN KT.

However, as explained, for cost reduction, energy savings, and increase of the size of the final components, I.FAST WP4.4 put in place a number of actions to find an alternative to MoGr, to be produced at lower temperature and bigger volumes. These actions led to the development of CrGr.

3 Development of Chromium-Graphite

In the first months of I.FAST, the WP4.4 team worked in parallel at the upscaling of the MoGr plate cross-section, up to Ø230 mm (Option #2 in Table 2) and at the development of CrGr, starting with an easier-to-master Ø170 mm plate size (Option #3 in Table 2). Production runs were made to address these two objectives, and results were presented in [10]; however, given the very promising initial results on CrGr, and considering that this material is the ultimate goal of WP4.4, Year 2 of the project was mostly dedicated to the consolidation of this material, *en route* to reaching Option #4 of Table 2.

The CrGr development was in the scope of the I.FAST milestone MS14, which was submitted in May 2022 [11]. We summarize here the main results, in particular for what concerns the sintering of Ø170 mm plates.

3.1 SINTERING OF Ø170 MM CRGR PLATES

After an initial R&D on small disks, allowing trying several parameters (temperature, pressure, chemical composition) to evaluate the optimal composition for CrGr, Nanoker moved to the production of Ø170 mm plates. Good results were achieved in 2021 and 2022 during two successive production runs, at a sintering temperature of 2000 °C maintained for 20 minutes under a 20 MPa pressure, and followed by an annealing treatment at 1700 °C for 3 hours. The difference between the two runs was the machine configuration: in the first run, a single Ø170 mm disk was sintered. In the second run, the machine configuration consisted in two Ø170 mm disks positioned one above the other, under the configuration shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

As an initial, quick assessment of the performance of the sintered plates, a density measurement was performed at Nanoker, together with an electrical conductivity test made with a Sigmatest® portable eddy current test instrument. During the MoGr production, in fact, it has been observed that the compaction rate (calculated out of the density measurement) and the electrical conductivity are good indicators of the quality of a CCM. These two properties are reported in Table 3 for the sintered Ø170 mm CrGr plates.

Table 3. Density and electrical conductivity of the CrGr Ø170 mm plates sintered by Nanoker in two successive runs in the large-size SPS machine.

Sintering Run	Production period	Plate number	Density (g/cm ³)	Electrical Conductivity (MS/m)
#1	November 2021	Plate #1	2.30	1,00 – 1,07
#2	March 2022	Plate #2	2.23	0.75 – 0.76
		Plate #3	2.29	0.80 – 0.81

Table 3 also shows that sintering run #2 was less favourable in terms of compaction and, consequently, electrical conductivity, than the previous sintering run. One possible reason for this is due to the different machine configuration, that can lead to worse homogeneity and heating distribution even for the same values of the parameters under control (temperature in the disk center, pressure and time). Another important difference between the two runs is that, in run #1, after reaching a temperature of 1850°C, the plate was maintained for 2 hours and a half at the same temperature, and progressively compacted, before finally applying the last 20min dwell at 2000°C. We considered that this led to a better material compaction, and the same principle of pre-dwell at 1850°C was adopted again when moving to larger plates of Ø230 mm (see Section 3.2.3 of this document).

3.2 CHARACTERIZATION OF OF Ø170 MM CRGR PLATES

In spite of a very likely still un-optimal material compaction, the results on CrGr were considered very positive, especially considering that these were the first production trials with the material at Nanoker. It was thus decided to perform an in-depth material characterization, to evaluate:

- Thermophysical properties, to be compared with requirements of Table 1
- Machinability
- Ultra-High Vacuum (UHV) behaviour

3.2.1 Thermophysical properties

The measurement of thermophysical properties required preparation of a set of samples, which were cut out of Plate #1, with reference to Table 3. All tests were performed in the EN-MME Mechanical Laboratory at CERN, with advanced instrumentations allowing to monitor the material properties over a wide range of temperatures. The main results are shown in the figures below.

Figure 4 – CrGr specific heat as a function of temperature.

Figure 5 – CrGr thermal diffusivity parallel (top) and perpendicular (bottom) to the basal plane.

Figure 6 – CrGr thermal expansion coefficient parallel (top) and perpendicular (bottom) to the basal plane.

Figure 7 – CrGr bending strength parallel (top) and perpendicular (bottom) to the basal plane.

A summary of the results, compared to the target properties of the CCM, is given in Table 4. In red, we highlight the values which do not fit yet with the material final target properties.

Table 4. CrGr properties compared to CCM targets.

Property	Specification		CrGr Plate #1		
	I*	F	I*	F	Unit
Density at 20°C	2.40 – 2.60		2.32		[g/cm ³]
Specific heat at 20°C	> 0.6		0.687		[J/(g·K)]
Electrical conductivity at 20°C	> 0.75		1.02		[MS/m]
Thermal Diffusivity 20°C / 300°C	> 350/100	> 20/6	470/120	33/9	[mm ² /s]
Thermal conductivity at 20°C / 300°C	> 500/280	> 35/20	750/350	52/27	[W/(m·K)]
Volumetric CTE 20-1000°C	< 7		6.7		[10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹]
Coefficient of thermal expansion 20-1000°C	< 2.9	< 15	4.0	12.0	[10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹]
Young’s Modulus at 20°C	35 < E < 75	5 < E < 8	46	3	[GPa]
Flexural strength at 20°C	> 60	> 10	58	8	[MPa]
Flexural strain to rupture at 20°C	> 2500	> 4000	3280	4200	[µm/m]
Dimensional stability	< 0.05	< 0.25	-0.05	0.45	%

With respect to the values not meeting yet the technical specification, one can observe that a density lower than 2.4 g/cm³ is not necessarily a malus, since it implies a lighter material, which is in general desirable for common applications. In particle beam-intercepting devices, a minimum density is required for beam absorption, but the reference in this sense are materials such as carbon-fibre carbon composites and isostatic graphite, used or proposed for use for example in the LHC collimation system. Such materials have a density of, respectively, 1.67 and 1.85 g/cm³, so a density in the order of 2.3 g/cm³ can generally be acceptable.

For what concerns the mechanical strength, although the value in the two directions is still slightly lower than the specification, a significant improvement (factor of 5-6) has been observed with respect the starting point of the project, where the baseline for CrGr was in the order of 10 MPa in the best direction.

The dimensional stability of the material is still not excellent, meaning that the samples are still in a state of internal stress induced by the production cycle and not completely removed by a subsequent 3h annealing cycle at 1700 °C. This result can easily be improved via optimization of the post-sintering annealing cycle.

3.2.2 Machinability

A key requirement for the industrial and research application of CCM is to have a material which can be produced in complex shapes and machined down to tight tolerances. Even though graphite and CCM are ceramic materials, they are well machinable, due to the relatively low Young modulus, and the non-negligible strain to rupture, as also shown, for CrGr, in Figure 7. To prove that this requirement is respected by CrGr, we decided to machine a block identical to those used as HL-LHC secondary collimator absorbers, see Annex B. The block has very tight tolerances, in particular for what concerns the flatness of the two big surfaces (0.01 mm on a 125x33 mm² surface). Moreover, in the case of MoGr, the CERN series production 2018/20 showed a phenomenon of relaxation with time of the machined part. This effect is problematic because, while stabilizing in the first ~1 month after machining, it requires a double-machining cycle that is time consuming and expensive. To understand if this phenomenon is present also in CrGr, three metrology measurements were performed at Nanoker, at different times after machining (one week, one month and two months). The block was then shipped to CERN and measured a fourth time. The tolerances of the three measurements were then compared to evaluate possible changes in the block, produced by material relaxation.

The CrGr block was machined at Nanoker in November 2022, out of the Plate #2 reported in Table 3. This is not ideal, since the material characterized thermophysically (section 3.2.1) came from the Plate #1. However, the material remaining from Plate #1 after the production of thermophysical samples was not enough to produce a full absorber block. Moreover, we expected that, adopting material from Plate #2, we would have been in a worst-case scenario, since the material produced in the sintering run #2 showed evidently un-optimal compaction, making it more difficult to machine.

Indeed, a problem occurred during machining of the block, due to delamination, which led to a corner defect (Figure 8). This is very likely due to the poor material compaction. However, in all the other regions of the block, tolerances are quite precise, see Table 5. Also, no significant change in tolerances occurred, hinting at the absence of relaxation of this block. Some difference can be found in the parallelism and position values measured at CERN. However, it is very unlikely that the material dimensionally changes after 3 months, whereas nothing happened for the first 2 months. When the relaxation was observed on MoGr, moreover, it tended to create a barrel-like effect on the blocks, which was also detrimental to their flatness. Here, this effect is not visible. It is thus more likely that the difference in position and parallelism are linked to the different way of defining the reference zone in the metrology measurement done at CERN with respect to those done at Nanoker.

Figure 8 – CrGr absorber block produced from Ø170 mm, Plate #2. Corner defect after machining is clearly visible. Also, porosities on the side surfaces are clear indication of un-optimal sintering, as already hinted by density and electrical conductivity measurement of this plate.

Figure 9 – CrGr absorber block, positioning for metrology measurement at CERN.

Table 5. Variation of tolerances of the CrGr absorber block after different post-machining time intervals.

Tolerance*	Time interval after machining			
	7 days	1 month	2 months	3 months
Flatness of “A” face [mm]	0.010	0.011	0.011	0.012
Flatness of face opposite to “A” (i.e. “Beam face”) [mm]	0.005	0.011	0.011	0.010
Parallelism of “Beam face” with respect to “A” [mm]	0.022	0.019	0.021	0.038
Position of “Beam face” with respect to “A” [mm]	0.025	0.022	0.021	0.042

*with reference to Annex B.

3.2.3 UHV behaviour

Whilst not relevant for many industrial applications, in the case of use in particle accelerator a UHV compatibility is required to the CCM. An outgassing and Residual-Gas Analysis (RGA) were then performed at CERN on the CrGr block machined and described in section 3.2.2. As per standard procedure to condition graphitic materials prior to UHV test/installation [12], the following operations were performed on the block before the UHV test:

- **Ultrasound cleaning**, to remove possible traces of contamination coming from machining/manipulation of the block. Method adopted was standard solvent cleaning procedure with a MEG machine [13] with ultrasonic agitation.

- **Vacuum firing**, a thermal treatment a high temperature to decrease material outgassing and burn possible residual traces of high-mass outgassing species. The thermal treatment was performed in a furnace under vacuum, at 850°C for 6h, with a post-cooldown venting with air at room temperature.

After these two operations, the block was placed in a vacuum chamber and tested according to [14]. The test includes a bakeout at 250°C for 48h, a following cooldown, and the total outgassing of the material is measured 48h and 96h after the end of the cooldown. Also, RGA scans are taken on the material 24h and 96h after the cooldown.

Figure 10 – Positioning of CrGr block in the UHV test bench vacuum chamber at CERN, courtesy of G. Cattenoz.

Results of the test are reported in Table 6 and Figure 11, and compared with acceptance thresholds for use in LHC collimators. The test confirms that CrGr can be considered, from UHV point of view, a viable alternative to MoGr and graphite in collimators. However, since the UHV behaviour can be influenced by the material compaction, it will be important to repeat this test on a more consolidated grade of CrGr (see sections 4 and **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Table 6. Outgassing of CrGr as a function of time.

Time after cooldown [h]	Specific outgassing [mbar·l/s/cm ²]	
	CrGr	Acceptance threshold*
48	$6.4 \cdot 10^{-12}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$
96	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-12}$	

**for installation in LHC collimators*

Figure 11 – Normalized RGA spectrum of CrGr, compared to acceptance limits for use in the LHC.

4 Production of upscaled-size Chromium-Graphite

The objective of deliverable D4.4 is the production of two Ø230 mm plates in the same sintering cycle. Given the positive results obtained on CrGr, and presented in the previous section of this document, the WP4.4 team decided to select it as the material of choice for the D4.4 sintering run.

The sintering run was performed in March 2023, and its configuration and results are reported in the next sub-sections.

4.1 MACHINE CONFIGURATION

The machined was prepared in a slightly different way with respect to the configuration used to sinter two Ø170mm plates in the same cycle, reported in Figure 2. Instead of adopting one mould for each plate, a single mould was used, common to both Ø230mm plates. Separation between the two plates was imposed by adding intermediate graphite disks, as visible in Figure 12.

Figure 12 – SPS machine configuration for the D4.4 sintering run. The machine hosted two Ø230mm CrGr plates in a single mould.

The final thickness targeted for each plate is 25 mm. Thanks to the large stroke available in the machine, it is very likely possible to go higher in thickness, up to an order of 50 mm. However, since all the experience gathered so far in CCM entails 25 mm thick plates, we decided to stick to this value to avoid changing too many parameters in the cycle. The increase in plate thickness will be one of the next steps in the material development, see section **Error! Reference source not found.**

4.2 MATERIAL COMPOSITION AND SINTERING PARAMETERS

We decided to adopt the same composition and sintering parameters as the most promising Plate #1 which was sintered with a Ø170 mm size, see Table 3.

Differences with respect to Plate #1, on top of the diameter and the number of plate in the machine cycle, were also related to the green body preparation. In Plate #1, the green body compaction was done under a pressure of 28 MPa, imposed by a cold press machine. However, increasing the plate cross-section, for the same maximum press force, the resulting pressure is lower (18 MPa). A summary of the parameters of the D4.4 sintering run is given below:

- Chemical composition (volumetric): 82.2% graphite 93004, 5% short carbon fibers “Cytek”, 1% titanium, 11.8% Chromium. Green body: pressure 18 MPa, green density 1.74 g/cm³.
- Sintering cycle: Pressure 25 MPa, pre-dwell 1850°C for 2.5h, dwell 2000°C for 20min.
- Sintered mass: 2 plates Ø230 mm, thickness 25 mm.

4.3 RESULTS

The sintering run was successfully performed on March 9th. The next paragraphs report the main results.

4.3.1 Cycle acquired data and energy balance

The cycle data, registered by the machine instrumentation, are reported in Figure 13.

Figure 13 – SPS machine data of the D4.4 sintering run.

A comparison between the temperature of the D4.4 sintering run with CrGr, and a standard double Ø170 mm MoGr cycle, can be seen in Figure 14. Figure 15 shows a similar comparison in terms of machine power.

Figure 14 – Comparison of the temperature during the sintering of 2 plates Ø170 mm in MoGr and 2 plates Ø230 mm in CrGr (note that the pyrometer starts recording above 300 °C).

Figure 15 – Comparison of power consumption for the sintering of 2 plates Ø170 mm in MoGr and 2 plates Ø230 mm in CrGr.

A few considerations can be done based on these observations:

- In spite of the addition of a 2.5h pre-dwell, the overall sintering time of CrGr is shorter, due to the lower temperature and faster heating ramp. This is favourable in terms of machine occupation, that translates into a cost (even when no power is injected in the machine).
- In spite of the lower sintering temperature, the peak power in the case of CrGr is higher. This is due to a combination of factor. Firstly, due to the faster heating ramps, the sintered body and insulation system are far from a steady state condition, and thus losses are higher. Moreover, because of the two times bigger plate cross-section area, the heated volume is larger, and more power is needed to reach the same temperature.

In any case, the peak power is not a parameter of particular interest, except for the fact that it must be lower than the maximum power that can be provided by the machine. No problem in this sense is observed: the required peak power is in the order of 150-200 kW, against a maximum machine power available up to 500 kW. What is, on the other hand, important for consumption and costs is the integral of power over time, which equals to the energy spent in the process. In terms of specific cost per unit of material volume, this energy must then be scaled to the quantity produced in the cycle. The outcome of this exercise is shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Energy consumption for different CCM sintering cycles.

	2x Ø170 MoGr plates	2x Ø230 CrGr plates	2x Ø230 CrGr plates without pre-dwell*
Energy per cycle [kWh]	408	577	214
Energy per cycle per material volume produced [kWh/cm³]	0.36	0.28	0.10
%Energy saving per material volume	<i>Pre-I.FAST baseline</i>	-23%	-72%

**Estimated from Figure 15*

It is evident that the D4.4 run resulted in an energy saving (-23%) per unit volume of material produced with respect to the pre-I.FAST baseline. However, the monitoring showed that most of the energy consumption occurred in the pre-dwell phase, that required 362 kWh over the total 577 kWh consumed. An estimation of a similar sintering run without pre-dwell results in even more important energy savings per volume of material (-72% with respect to baseline).

For what we have observed during the CrGr development (see section 3), it is unlikely that the pre-dwell can be completely skipped, due to its importance for material compaction. Indeed, first thermophysical measurements done on the D4.4 sintering run gave a very positive outcome, see section 4.3.3. However, optimizing the pre-dwell duration, possibly reducing it to 1h-1h30m, is a future way of further increasing the efficiency, and reducing the cost, of the process.

4.3.2 Plate extraction and mould saving

Several interesting observations could be made once extracting the mould from the machine, at the end of the cycle. For example, Figure 16 shows a significant amount of molten chromium carbide flowing out of the mould and solidifying during cooldown. While the presence of the liquid phase helps obtaining a better graphitization of the graphite matrix, an excessive amount can be detrimental: the molten material is wasted, and could also procure damage to the SPS machine components. A possible decrease of the chromium content in next trials could be envisaged.

Figure 16 – Mould extraction after D4.4 sintering run: note the extensive presence of molten chromium carbides, which flew out of the mould during the cycle.

A very positive result is that the CrGr plates could be extracted from the mould without damaging it (Figure 17). This is an important improvement with respect to the production of MoGr, which required destruction of the mould(s) during each cycle, at high cost. With respect to the configuration of Figure 12, only one intermediate graphite disk was found with a surface crack after disassembling.

Figure 17 – Extraction of one CrGr plate from the mould.

The two sintered plates could be extracted from the mould without any difficulty, see Figure 18.

Figure 18 – 2x Ø230mm CrGr plates after extraction from the mould.

4.3.3 Electrical conductivity and density measurements

After the extraction of the CrGr plates, electrical conductivity, in several locations, and density measurements were performed at Nanoker. Results can be compared with previous CrGr sintering runs, see Table 8.

Table 8. Density and electrical conductivity of all CrGr Ø170 mm plates sintered by Nanoker.

Sintering Run	Production period	Plate number	Diameter (cm)	Density (g/cm ³)	Electrical Conductivity (MS/m)
#1*	November 2021	Plate #1	170	2.30	1,00 – 1,07
#2*	March 2022	Plate #2	170	2.23	0.75 – 0.76
		Plate #3	170	2.29	0.80 – 0.81
#3 (D4.4)	March 2023	Plate #4	230	2.44	0.86 – 1.05
		Plate #5	230	2.44	0.91 – 0.94

*values after stress-relaxation annealing cycle at 1700°C

Conductivity (MS/m)			Conductivity (MS/m)		
Position	Side 1	Side 2	Position	Side 1	Side 2
1	1,04	0,74	1	0,95	0,92
2	1,02	0,75	2	0,94	0,93
3	1,03	0,79	3	0,94	0,90
4	1,04	0,78	4	0,95	0,88
5	1,08	0,89	5	0,93	0,91
6	1,06	0,94	6	0,93	0,93
7	1,01	0,88	7	0,93	0,92
8	1,09	0,96	8	0,94	0,91
9	1,05	1,00	9	0,92	0,93
Average	1,05	0,86	Average	0,94	0,91

Figure 19 – Map of electrical conductivity measurements on the two sides of each Ø230 mm CrGr plate sintered during D4.4 run.

It is evident that the properties of the last two sintered CrGr plates are very good, and in line with the single-plate cycle performed in November 2021. Density is even higher, but these values are taken, on Plates #4 and #5, before the 1700°C annealing cycle, which will release internal stresses and expand the material, decreasing its density. We believe that this positive result is due to the pre-dwell at 1850°C, which was absent in Plates #2 and #3.

5 Conclusions and future plans

During the first two years of the project, WP4.4 achieved important results in the development of CCM. A viable, cheaper alternative to MoGr was found to be CrGr. In March 2023, a sintering run was successfully performed, producing two Ø230 mm CrGr plates with good compaction and electrical conductivity. This sintering run fulfils the deliverable D4.4, achieving two main goals:

1. Sintering CCM at lower temperature, leading to the saving of mould elements and to lower specific energy consumption.
2. Sintering two bigger CCM plates in a single machine cycle., allowing production of larger components for industrial and research application.

The material produced during the D4.4 sintering run needs now to be extensively characterized. From there, possible additional actions can be envisaged for even better cost optimization. Starting with the material characterization, we plan to repeat the tests described in section 3.2 of this document, both on samples and on precisely machined components. Before that, however, we plan to evaluate the real need of the annealing cycle: cutting this from the production sequence would, in fact, be beneficial cost-wise. This can be done testing the expansion of small samples after different thermal cycles, to be performed in a dilatometer, with the additional added value of allowing measurement of the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). The testing sequence on Plates #4 and #5 will thus be:

1. Machining and testing of samples, in a dilatometer, evaluating the relaxation after different thermal cycles, and the CTE of the material. This will allow optimizing the annealing cycle, or possibly removing it from the production sequence.
2. Annealing cycle on the remaining material, based on the results of point 1. This step could ideally be skipped, if tests at point 1 show that it is not needed.
3. Machining of samples for full thermophysical characterization at CERN, and testing of such samples.
4. Production of 1-2 blocks as per Annex B, to evaluate machinability and UHV properties at CERN.

With the results of the full characterization, it will then be possible to explore future actions on CrGr, to be taken during the last two years of the project, with the goal of minimizing the production costs. Additionally, if results of the characterization will highlight technical shortcomings, those shall be addressed and resolved.

In terms of beneficial actions for cost reduction, some of the possibilities are:

- Removal of the annealing cycle, as already mentioned.
- Decrease of the duration / temperature of the pre-dwell during sintering. This step, while technically important, has proved to be very energy-consuming.
- Optimization of the insulation system. This could lead to lower energy loss and thus lower energy required to the sintering cycle.
- Increase of the thickness of the sintered plates, up to 5 cm looks ideally possible. Alternatively, increase of the number of sintered plates, up to 4. While this second option, in terms of sintered volume, is equivalent, it is considered to be less appealing, because specific applications could benefit of a higher achievable thickness.
- Minimization of the amount of chromium-carbide in the initial composition, to avoid wasting a lot of material, which melts and flows out of the mould during sintering.

6 References

- [1]. Bertarelli A., Carra F., Garlaschè M., Gradassi P., Guardia-Valenzuela J., Sgobba S., Tsarfati T. (2015) Innovative MoC-graphite composite for thermal management and thermal shock applications, *Proc. 31st Annual Semiconductor Thermal Measurement and Management Symposium (SEMI-THERM)*: San Jose, CA USA, March 15-19, 2015, 56-59, DOI: [10.1109/SEMI-THERM.2015.7100140](https://doi.org/10.1109/SEMI-THERM.2015.7100140).
- [2]. Tvede L. (2021) Materials that matter, *CERN article*, <https://kt.cern/news/news/spotlight-series/materials-matter>.
- [3]. Guardia-Valenzuela J., Bertarelli A., Carra F., Mariani N. Bizzaro S., Arenal R. (2018) Development and properties of high thermal conductivity molybdenum carbide - graphite composites, *Carbon*, Volume 135, pp. 72-84.
- [4]. ARIES website, <https://aries.web.cern.ch/>.
- [5]. Carra F. (2019) A novel composite for HL-LHC collimators, *Accelerating News*, 12 July 2019, <https://acceleratingnews-d7-archive.web.cern.ch/node/128.html>.
- [6]. Aberle O. *et al.* (2020) High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC): Technical design report, *CERN report CERN-2020-010*, doi.org/10.23731/CYRM-2020-0010.
- [7]. Guardia-Valenzuela J. (2019) Optimisation of graphite-matrix composites for collimators in the LHC upgrade, *PhD thesis*, [10.5281/zenodo.5837352](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5837352).
- [8]. Bertarelli A. (2022) Materials for extreme thermal management: report from WP17, *presentation given at the 5th ARIES Annual Meeting*, Geneva, Switzerland, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1128531/>.
- [9]. Carra F. (2019) A novel composite for HL-LHC collimators, *Accelerating News*, 12 July 2019, <https://acceleratingnews-d7-archive.web.cern.ch/node/128.html>.
- [10]. Carra F. (2022) Carbide-carbon materials for multipurpose applications, *presentation given at the 1st IFAST Annual Meeting*, Geneva, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1133254/>.
- [11]. Carra F., Accettura C., Guardia-Valenzuela J., Rivera S., Gutierrez C., Sacristan de Frutos O., Hoell S. (2022) Evaluation of a Carbide Carbon Material (CCM) alternative to Molybdenum-Graphite, *I.Fast Milestone MS14*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6977230>.
- [12]. Accettura C. (2017) UHV characterization of advanced materials and their coatings, *presentation given at the 1st Workshop of ARIES PowerMat (WP17)*, Turin, Italy, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/667373>.
- [13]. MEG website <http://www.meg.it/en/company>.
- [14]. Accettura C. *et al.* (2019) Ultra-High Vacuum characterization of Molybdenum-Carbide Graphite for HL-LHC collimators, *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **1350** 012085, DOI 10.1088/1742-6596/1350/1/012085.

Annex A: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
CCM	Carbide-Carbon Materials
HEP	High-Energy Physics
BID	Beam-Intercepting Devices
KT	Knowledge Transfer
SPS	Spark Plasma Sintering
MoGr	Molybdenum-Graphite
CrGr	Chromium-Graphite
CTE	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

